

Archives and Database: The Chronicle of Modern Translation Literature in Chinese (Periodicals, 1896-1949)

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Fig.1 The Cover Page of the Database

The database “The Chronicle of Modern Translation Literature in Chinese (Periodicals, 1896-1949) #####(###, 1896-1949)” is a literary database jointly designed by scholars specializing in modern Chinese literature studies and China Bookstore Gulian Digital Media Co. It collects 9456 entries on Chinese translation literature from 225 distinct periodicals, covering original works, original authors, translators, and brief descriptions of translated works, involving as many as 2130 translators, 1580 foreign writers, 9456 translated works, and relevant theories and reviews.

Fig.2 The Periodicals Included in the Database

The database was set up on Chinese scholars’ textual research. The contents of their research are as follows: First, under each translation item the scholars verify the original names and the current translated names of the authors and the works, as well as the real names and the common names of the translators. The standardization of them will be convenient for the scholars to search and do the related study. Second, the scholars do a textual research on the short biographies of the authors and the translators, as well as the versions, the sources, the purposes, the strategies and the forms of the translations. Third, the scholars summarize the reviews on the foreign authors, the works, the translation theories, the translation activities and so on.

The database has three principal functions: First, it allows thematic search with related terms. By pre-examining the primary archives, the IT technicians further set up the thematic search, establishing the connection between the original names and the current translated names of the authors and the works, the translators’ real names as well as their pen names and their common names based on the synonym function of computer natural language processing. For instance, in the two search modes provided by the database, full-text search and keyword search, when the name of the translator is entered, such as Lu Xun###, the information related to the pen names he used, such as Suo Zi##, Feng Sheng##, and Du Wen##, will pop up at the same time; in addition, his relevant information will be presented. When Guy de Maupassant### is entered, all the translated names of him in Chinese, such as ### Mengbasang, ### Mobasang, ### Yupusang, ### Mobosan, and ## #Maobaisang will appear. The thematic search provides a general picture of the terms for researchers and thus better facilitates their research.

Fig.3 The Thematic Search

Second, it has a built-in index of classified terms. We increase the weight assigned to the terms in the search and provide advanced search by subjects such as original author, translator, the title of work, genre, nationality, and periodical.

tracted from 239 distinct periodicals and provides careful examination collation, introductory overview, and visualization for each entry. It breaks the subjective narration of literary history and presents the original and complicated situation of the literary history.

Fig.4 The Advanced Search by Title

Third, the database enables a chronological reading mode. Considering the cross-cultural and translanguagual nature of Chinese translation literature, which may cause difficulties in interpretation, it designs an auxiliary mechanism that enables the instant float of the profiles of original authors, translators, journals, etc. on the basis of chronological reading mode. This function allows readers to have a more comprehensive understanding of the keyword they require. It provides the photocopy of the first edition of translation works and thereby readers can easily verify the OCR text with the original text.

Fig.5 The Chronological Reading Mode

Fig.6 The Photocopy of the First Edition of a Translation Work

Concluding remark, this database includes a large quantity of Chinese translation literature from 1896-1949 chronologically ex-